

Model-based biomimetic approach for compliance discrimination through soft tactile optical sensing

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Abstract—Soft tactile optical sensors offer new possibilities for enhancing artificial robotic hands with advanced touch capabilities. However, their application for compliance discrimination mainly relies on data-driven techniques. This study introduces the first attempt to discriminate compliance using soft optical tactile sensing based on a computational model inspired by human tactile perception, utilizing Contact Area Spread Rate (CASR) and tactile flow concepts. We employed a soft optical biomimetic sensor, translating surface deformation into marked pin movements. By acquiring images of marker movements during interactions with silicone specimens of different compliance levels and indenting forces, we estimated CASR through optical flow approximation and divergence. We accurately differentiated the compliance levels of specimens with our model-based approach and also inferred compliance for new specimens.

I. INTRODUCTION

The sense of touch is crucial for humans to explore and interact with the world, providing information about object characteristics such as compliance. Compliance and its subjective perceptual counterpart, softness, are important physical properties and provide valuable information after the initial phases of contact [1], influencing object grasping and manipulation [2].

Incorporating tactile cutaneous feedback in engineering devices allows for precise control, improved performance, and an enhanced user experience [3], [4]. Artificial systems, such as robotic hands, can benefit from studying human touch and biomimicry. In that sense, soft tactile optical sensors show promise in estimating object properties based on their similarity to human cutaneous sensing [5], [6]. However, only Data-driven approaches have been employed, but they have limitations in data quality and dimensionality and also neglect human tactile perception processes. When considering integrating optical tactile sensors with prosthetic robotic hands and closing the action-perception loop with prosthesis users, this limitation becomes significant since, to achieve effective sensory restoration, we need to focus on providing the same kind of stimuli that natural touch perception uses for perceiving softness, Modality Matching (MM) [7]. On the contrary, model-based methods could offer a more robust and cost-effective solution. In [8], the authors propose, for the first time, a model-based approach for compliance estimation by applying optical flow analysis to data of a soft biomimetic optical tactile sensor that mimics the human fingertip, TacTip [9], [10]. This estimation is based on the observed contact

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Fig. 1: Schematic describing the complete pipeline.

area spread rate paradigm and tactile flow computation, which are derived from behavioral and neuroscientific studies on human tactile perception [11]. By computing the optical flow of images acquired during the indentation of silicone specimens with varying compliance, we estimate the tactile flow indirectly. The divergence of the optical flow, correlated to the indenting force, is then used to estimate CASR during contact. Providing an approximate relation between compliance and the CASR, we demonstrate that our strategy allows inferring the compliance of new unknown specimens.

II. THE BIOMIMETIC APPROACH

Our approach relies on the TacTip sensor, computing optical flow from captured images as tactile flow approximation and the connection between the divergence of the optical flow and the CASR for discriminating softness. The TacTip is a tactile sensor that imitates the structure of glabrous skin and incorporates a system of rigid inner nodular pins endowed with markers to convert surface indentation into shear strain, enabling touch detection [9]. The *tactile flow model* is a computational model introduced in [12] to study the tactile perception of dynamic stimuli. The CASR paradigm shows that the pattern of tactile stimulus can provide information on the compliance of probed objects and demonstrates the relationship between contact area dilatation and tactile flow,

$$\frac{dA_c}{dF} = \oint_c \vec{\phi} \cdot \vec{n} \, dl = \iint_{A_c} \nabla \cdot \vec{\phi} \, dA, \quad (1)$$

where F is the force, A_c is the area comprised in the iso-SED contour c , $\vec{\phi} \cdot \vec{n}$ is the SED flow vector component normal to the contour, and $\nabla \cdot \vec{\phi}$ is the *divergence* of the flow.

Since the tactile flow definition is equivalent to the optical flow one, we adopted a dense optical flow estimation technique, i.e., the Horn-Schunck method, to approximate the tactile flow for the estimation of the pin’s expansion on the entire TacTip sensible area. This expansion is similar to the radial patterns of iso-brightness contours used in vision to estimate the time-to-contact of an approaching object, for which the derivative of the area is defined as the product between the area of a closed contour and the divergence [13]. Therefore, we use this definition to evaluate the CASR of the TacTip surface, considering the derivative of the area

Fig. 2: (a) and (b) show CASR discrimination based on the proposed model. Different specimens are color-coded, respectively, S_1 in blu, S_2 in green, and S_3 in yellow.

with respect to the probing force during the contact with the specimens. Once obtained the dense optical flow, we compute the divergence \mathcal{D} as the summation on the whole camera image of the sum of the optical flow partial derivatives, and we defined the cumulative divergence \mathcal{D}_{cum} as the summation of the divergence of the dense optical flow in a frame sequence. Then, the contact area correspondent to the probing force F_i at the i -th frame is evaluated as $A_{c_i} = A_{c_0} e^{\mathcal{D}_{cum} F_i}$, where A_{c_0} is the initial area estimated in the static condition of the TacTip. Finally, we evaluated $\frac{dA_{c_i}}{dF_i}$ at frame i as,

$$\frac{dA_{c_i}}{dF_i} = \sum_{j=1}^i \frac{A_{c_j} - A_{c_{j-1}}}{F_j - F_{j-1}}, \quad (2)$$

taking into consideration $F_0 = 0$. We use the CASR, estimated for each frame sequence, to discriminate possible different levels of the softness of the explored objects. Fig. 1 depicts a schematic of the complete method pipeline.

III. PRELIMINARY EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

As a proof of concept, we indented three cylindrical silicone specimens (S_1, S_2, S_3) (height: 40 mm, radius: 20 mm), realized by mixing a given quantity of Sylgard 184 silicone in different compositions, with an increasing probing force along the direction perpendicular to the top surface. We used an ABS smooth plate as a tactile tool to characterize the specimens. Considering a linear model (worst adjusted R-squared of 0.882) fitted between filtered aligned contact force and deformation collected during the experiment we estimated stiffness values equal to $\kappa_{S_1} = 7.6, \kappa_{S_2} = 3.1, \kappa_{S_3} = 1.1$ N/mm. In the experiments, the speed of the tactile tool was kept constant at 5 mm/s to stay within the elastic domain of contacts where Hertz's theory applies.

After, we used the TacTip sensor to validate our novel model-based approach. We tested the specimens five times, and for each trial, the raw and filtered contact forces, the actual position of the support, and the associated camera frame index, collected with the TacTip, were saved for data analysis. The collected data were truncated in the range $[0.5, 5]$ N of the filtered contact force to take into account only what happens during the contact phase. These data were the input for the evaluation the of contact area and CASR for each trial and specimen. As is shown in Fig. 2a, differences between CASR values were only evident when a sufficient force value was reached, which is consistent with human cutaneous object compliance recognition, so the data samples have been modified considering only the CASR values corresponding to force values greater than 2.5 N. Based on the Kruskalwallis test, we

can assert that the data samples are statistically different with a p -value $\approx 6.3e - 5$, and the post-hoc lsd correction shows p -value ≈ 0.01 in the worst case. Fig. 2b presents the boxplot of each CASR evaluated on the data samples, showing that a good discrimination of the softness level can be obtained with the proposed model-based approach based on the contact area instead of on the deformation.

IV. DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

This work introduces a novel model-based approach for discriminating compliance using soft tactile optical sensing. It is based on tactile flow and CASR concepts and leverages the analogies between vision and touch. By computing the optical flow of images captured by the TacTip sensor and exploiting divergence as done in time-to-contact experiments, we were able to estimate the compliance of an object. Since our estimation is based on controlling the contact area on the skin using stimuli from optical tactile biomimetic sensors, we can achieve a successful restoration of softness perception allowing for the effective implementation of the MM approach. With this approach, we can retrieve contact area growth information and use it to control skin stimulation, aligning it with human tactile perception. In this work we report a proof of concept demonstration of our approach: in future work, we plan a test with more specimens and the the integration of the sensor with soft robotic grippers and wearable haptics technology and extensive tests with robotics-enabled prostheses and telerobotics.

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